

Plant-based

Fermentation

Cultivated

Finland's alternative protein research ecosystem

Leading research organisations

Unique publications

Alternative proteins – plant-based, fermentation-derived or cultivated – offer a promising solution to meet the projected growth in the global demand for meat, seafood, eggs, and dairy, while building a more sustainable food system.

184 publications

#11 in publication volume in Europe
+100% from 2020 to 2025

412 patents

#7 in published patent volume in Europe

Total public funding

Million € · 2020-2025

Funding per capita

€ per person · 2020-2025

If the EU makes alternative proteins a strategic priority, the sector could contribute significantly to the bloc's economy by 2040.

€111B

annual economic contribution

+400,000

jobs supported